

SINGULARITY ANALYSIS OF THE IOSIPESCU SHEAR SPECIMEN

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ABSTRACT

Using classical theory of elasticity, a singularity analysis is performed at the notch tip of an Iosipescu shear specimen. Numerical results for a 90° notch indicate that the presence of a singularity depends on material properties. For example, a singularity is not found in conjunction with isotropic materials or 90° unidirectional graphite/epoxy composites. Singularities are obtained, however, for 0° unidirectional composites and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminates constructed from graphite/epoxy material.

INTRODUCTION

The Iosipescu (or v-notch) specimen is illustrated in Fig. 1. This specimen configuration produces a zero moment at the notch cross-section, which, according to classical strength-of-materials, will lead to pure shear (normal stress vanishes). The notch is obviously introduced to assure failure at this cross-section where the assumed state-of-stress is pure shear.

Figure 1. Iosipescu shear specimen.

According to Iosipescu's original work [1], no stress concentration exists at the v-notch for isotropic materials. However, work by Williams [2] indicated the potential for a singularity with respect to v-shaped notches in isotropic plates under a general case of inplane loading.

In the present paper, the question of a singularity at the notch tip of an Iosipescu specimen is addressed for both isotropic and orthotropic materials. The model utilized is more specific to the Iosipescu specimen than the general plane stress case considered by Williams. In addition, unlike Williams, orthotropic materials are considered.

SINGULARITY ANALYSIS FOR ORTHOTROPIC MATERIALS

In the singularity analysis, we assume that there is sufficient distance between the interior loads so that St. Venant's principle applies. In such a case the loading is idealized as shown in Fig. 2, which results in anti-symmetric behavior (i.e. we assure that σ_x vanishes at the notch cross-section). Under this condition we consider the right-side of the notch section and focus on the region near the notch tip. For convenience we choose the coordinate system shown in Fig. 3 with the y axis running along the length of the beam and the x axis oriented in the thickness direction. For a 90° notch the angle α is obviously 45°.

Figure 2. Idealized loading with the St. Venant effect dissipated.

For the V-Notch specimen, the beam will be under plane stress conditions. A stress function, Φ , is chosen in the form

$$\Phi = \frac{A_1(Z_1^{\delta+2} + \bar{Z}_1^{\delta+2}) + i A_2(Z_1^{\delta+2} - \bar{Z}_1^{\delta+2}) + A_3(Z_2^{\delta+2} + \bar{Z}_2^{\delta+2}) + i A_4(Z_2^{\delta+2} - \bar{Z}_2^{\delta+2})}{(\delta + 1)(\delta + 2)} \quad (1)$$

where Z_1 are functions of the complex variables $x + i\mu y$ and \bar{Z}_1 are complex conjugates $x - i\mu y$. Denoting partial differentiation by a comma, the stress function must satisfy the following compatibility condition

$$\frac{E_1}{E_2} \Phi_{,xxxx} + \frac{(E_1 - 2\nu_{12})}{G_{12}} \Phi_{,xxyy} + \Phi_{,yyyy} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where E_1 and E_2 are moduli in the x and y directions, respectively, and G_{12} denotes the shear modulus relative to the x-y plane. In addition, ν_{12} denotes the Poisson's ratio as determined from a uniaxial tensile test in the x-direction, measuring contraction in the y-direction. Substituting eq. (1) into eq. (2) we obtain the following characteristic polynomial

$$\mu^4 + \frac{(E_1 - 2G_{12})}{G_{12}} \mu^2 + \frac{E_1}{E_2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

In general μ is complex, however, for most engineering materials it is real and of the form

$$\mu_{1,2} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{E_1}{G_{12}} - 2\nu_{12} \right] \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{E_1}{G_{12}} - 2\nu_{12} \right)^2 - 4 \frac{E_1}{E_2}}} \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) is applicable to any composite laminate with orthotropic inplane properties.

Figure 3. Nomenclature for singularity analysis ($\alpha = 45^\circ$ for a 90° notch).

Stresses are determined from the stress function in the usual manner, i.e.,

$$\sigma_x = \Phi_{,yy}, \quad \sigma_y = \Phi_{,xx}, \quad \tau_{xy} = -\Phi_{,xy} \quad (5)$$

where σ_x and σ_y are normal stresses in the x and y directions, respectively, and τ_{xy} is the shear stress relative to the x-y plane. Combining eqs. (1) and (5), we obtain the following stresses

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x &= -\mu_1^2 A_1 (Z_1^\delta + \bar{Z}_1^\delta) - i\mu_1^2 A_2 (Z_1^\delta - \bar{Z}_1^\delta) - \mu_2^2 A_3 (Z_2^\delta + \bar{Z}_2^\delta) - i\mu_2^2 A_4 (Z_2^\delta - \bar{Z}_2^\delta) \\ \sigma_y &= A_1 (Z_1^\delta + \bar{Z}_1^\delta) + i A_2 (Z_1^\delta - \bar{Z}_1^\delta) + A_3 (Z_2^\delta + \bar{Z}_2^\delta) + i A_4 (Z_2^\delta - \bar{Z}_2^\delta) \\ \tau_{xy} &= -i\mu_1 A_1 (Z_1^\delta - \bar{Z}_1^\delta) + \mu_1 A_2 (Z_1^\delta + \bar{Z}_1^\delta) - i\mu_2 A_3 (Z_2^\delta - \bar{Z}_2^\delta) + \mu_2 A_4 (Z_2^\delta + \bar{Z}_2^\delta) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

From the stress-strain relations we have

$$u_{,x} = \frac{1}{E_1} (\Phi_{,yy} - \nu_{12} \Phi_{,xx}), \quad v_{,y} = \left(\frac{1}{E_2} \Phi_{,xx} - \frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} \Phi_{,yy} \right) \quad (7)$$

where u and v denote displacements in the x and y directions, respectively. Substituting the stress function from eq. (1) and integrating u with respect to x and v with respect to y we obtain

the following displacements

$$u = -\frac{(\mu_1^2 + \nu_{12})}{E_1(\delta + 1)} [A_1 (Z_1^{\delta+1} + \bar{Z}_1^{\delta+1}) + i A_2 (Z_1^{\delta+1} - \bar{Z}_1^{\delta+1})] - \frac{(\mu_2^2 + \nu_{12})}{E_1(\delta + 1)} [A_3 (Z_2^{\delta+1} + \bar{Z}_2^{\delta+1}) + i A_4 (Z_2^{\delta+1} - \bar{Z}_2^{\delta+1})] \quad (8)$$

$$v = \frac{(E_1 + \mu_1^2 \nu_{12} E_2)}{i \mu_1 E_1 E_2 (\delta + 1)} [A_1 (Z_1^{\delta+1} - \bar{Z}_1^{\delta+1}) + i A_2 (Z_1^{\delta+1} + \bar{Z}_1^{\delta+1})] + \frac{(E_1 + \mu_2^2 \nu_{12} E_2)}{i \mu_2 E_1 E_2 (\delta + 1)} [A_3 (Z_2^{\delta+1} - \bar{Z}_2^{\delta+1}) + i A_4 (Z_2^{\delta+1} + \bar{Z}_2^{\delta+1})]$$

The coefficients A_i are determined from the following boundary conditions for $\alpha = 45^\circ$

$$\text{At } y = 0, u = \sigma_x = 0; \text{ At } x = -y, y > 0, \sigma_x' = \tau_{xy}' = 0 \quad (9)$$

Using stress transformation relations, the second of eqs. (9) becomes

$$\text{At } x = -y, y > 0, \sigma_x - \sigma_y = 0; \sigma_y + \tau_{xy} = 0 \quad (10)$$

Boundary conditions at $y = 0$ lead to the vanishing of A_1 and A_3 , while eq. (10) in conjunction with the stresses, eq. (6), leads to the following results

$$\begin{bmatrix} (1+\mu_1^2)^{(\delta+2)/2} \sin \delta \theta_1 & (1+\mu_2^2)^{(\delta+2)/2} \sin \delta \theta_2 \\ (1+\mu_1^2)^{\delta/2} (\sin \delta \theta_1 - \mu_1 \cos \delta \theta_1) & (1+\mu_2^2)^{\delta/2} (\sin \delta \theta_2 - \mu_2 \cos \delta \theta_2) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_2 \\ A_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where

$$\theta_1 = \pi - \arctan \mu_1, \quad \theta_2 = \pi - \arctan \mu_2$$

In order to avoid a trivial solution to these two homogeneous, algebraic equations, δ is chosen such that the determinant of the coefficient matrix vanishes. This leads to the transcendental equation

$$(1+\mu_1^2) \sin \delta \theta_1 (\sin \delta \theta_2 - \mu_2 \cos \delta \theta_2) - (1+\mu_2^2) \sin \delta \theta_2 (\sin \delta \theta_1 - \mu_1 \cos \delta \theta_1) = 0 \quad (12)$$

There are an infinite number of values of δ , either real or complex, which will satisfy this relationship. For the purpose of identifying singularities at the notch tip, we are interested in $-1 < \delta < 0$. For $\delta \leq -1$, unbounded displacements will occur.

SINGULARITY ANALYSIS FOR ISOTROPIC MATERIALS

For the case of isotropic materials we will consider the two notch geometries illustrated in Fig. 4. The geometry in Fig. 4(a) corresponds to one of the boundary conditions considered by Williams [2] for the general case of plane stress loading of isotropic materials in conjunction

with a boundary notch. As in the case for orthotropic materials, the half notch shown in Fig. 4(b) allows us to consider conditions more specific to the Iosipescu shear specimen.

Figure 4. Isotropic singularity analysis: (a) full notch; (b) half notch.

For isotropic materials the form of the stress function changes and eq. (1) is not valid. Using polar coordinates, the governing equations in terms of a stress function have been presented by Williams [2]. For the boundary conditions shown in Fig. 4 it is only necessary to consider the stress components σ_θ and $\tau_{r\theta}$ in conjunction with the tangential displacement u_θ . These functions are of the form [2]

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_\theta &= (\delta + 1)(\delta + 2)r^\delta [A_1 \sin(\delta + 2)\theta + A_2 \cos(\delta + 2)\theta + A_3 \sin \delta\theta + A_4 \cos \delta\theta] \\ \tau_{r\theta} &= -(\delta + 1)r^\delta [A_1(\delta + 2) \cos(\delta + 2)\theta + A_2(\delta + 2) \sin(\delta + 2)\theta \\ &\quad + A_3 \delta \cos \delta\theta + A_4 \delta \sin \delta\theta] \\ 2Gu_\theta &= r^{(\delta + 1)} \left\{ -A_1(\delta + 2) \cos(\delta + 2)\theta + A_2(\delta + 2) \sin(\delta + 2)\theta \right. \\ &\quad \left. - A_3 \left[\delta + \frac{4\nu}{(1 + \nu)} \right] \cos \delta\theta + A_4 \left[\delta + \frac{4\nu}{(1 + \nu)} \right] \sin \delta\theta \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Here the angle θ is measured from the x-axis with positive angles rotating in the counterclockwise direction according to a right hand rule. We note from Fig. 4 that the boundary condition at $\theta = 0$ is the same for both the full notch and the half notch, i.e.

$$\text{At } \theta = 0, \sigma_\theta = \tau_{r\theta} = 0 \quad (14)$$

Substituting eq. (13) into this boundary condition, we find that

$$A_4 = -A_2, \quad A_3 = -\frac{(\delta + 2)}{\delta} A_1 \quad (15)$$

In the case of the full notch eq. (14) is also applicable at $\theta = -3\pi/2$ with the result

$$\begin{bmatrix} (\delta + 1) \sin \frac{3\delta\pi}{2} & -\delta \cos \frac{3\delta\pi}{2} \\ (\delta + 2) \cos \frac{3\delta\pi}{2} & (\delta + 1) \sin \frac{3\delta\pi}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_1 \\ A_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Again the trivial solution is avoided by considering values of δ which lead to a zero determinant of the coefficient matrix in eq. (16). The resulting eigenvalue equation is given by

$$\cos \frac{3\delta\pi}{2} = \pm (\delta + 1) \quad (17)$$

In addition to equation (14), the following boundary condition is applicable for the half notch:

$$\text{At } \theta = -\frac{3\pi}{4}, \quad \sigma_\theta = u_\theta = 0 \quad (18)$$

Substituting eqs. (13) into eq. (18), taking into account eq. (15), we obtain the following homogeneous equations:

$$\left[\begin{array}{cc} [\delta \cos \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} + (\delta+2) \sin \frac{3\delta\pi}{4}] & \delta [\sin \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} - \cos \frac{3\delta\pi}{4}] \\ (\delta+2) \left\{ \delta \sin \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} - \left[\delta - \frac{4\nu}{(1+\nu)} \right] \cos \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} \right\} & \delta \left\{ (\delta+2) \cos \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} + \left[\delta - \frac{4\nu}{(1+\nu)} \right] \sin \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} \right\} \end{array} \right] \times \begin{bmatrix} A_1 \\ A_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

The resulting eigenvalue equation is of the form

$$\begin{aligned} & [\delta \cos \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} + (\delta+2) \sin \frac{3\delta\pi}{4}] \left\{ (\delta+2) \cos \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} + \left[\delta - \frac{4\nu}{(1+\nu)} \right] \sin \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} \right\} \\ & + (\delta+2) \left(\sin \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} - \cos \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} \right) \left\{ \delta \sin \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} - \left[\delta - \frac{4\nu}{(1+\nu)} \right] \cos \frac{3\delta\pi}{4} \right\} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

As in the case of orthotropic materials, singularities are associated with $-1 < \delta < 0$, as unbounded displacements will occur for $\delta \leq -1$.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The first five eigenvalues to eq. (12) are shown in Table 1 for $[0^\circ]$ and a $[90^\circ]$, unidirectional composite. A bidirectional, $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$, laminate is also shown in Table 1. Laminate properties are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{E_1}{E_2} &= 15.4, \quad \frac{G_{12}}{E_2} = 0.615, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.3, \quad [0^\circ] \\ \frac{E_1}{E_2} &= 0.065, \quad \frac{G_{12}}{E_2} = 0.04, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.0195, \quad [90^\circ] \\ \frac{E_1}{E_2} &= 1, \quad \frac{G_{12}}{E_2} = 0.0748, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.0366, \quad [0^\circ/90^\circ]_S \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

The properties in eq. (21) are typical of state-of-the-art graphite/epoxy composites. Results for an isotropic material with a Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$ are shown in Table 2 for both the full notch and the half notch. The first column represents the full notch and corresponds to Williams analysis [2], while the second column contains results from the half notch. It should be noted that the mixed boundary condition represented by eq. (18) for the half notch is not a condition considered by Williams [2].

Eigenvalues in Tables 1 and 2 are determined from *Mathematica* which employs the Newton-

Rapson method. Real roots were cross-checked using an iteration scheme. It should be noted that 0 is a root to eq. (12).

Table 1. First Five Non-Zero Eigenvalues to Eq. (12)

[0°]	[90°]	[0°/90°] _S
-0.2466	0.1435	-0.0586
1.116 ± 0.1665 i	1.6060 ± 0.1981 i	1.2233
2.355 ± 0.0495 i	2.8685	1.5361
3.288	3.4194	2.2731
3.913	4.0689	3.3208 ± 0.1104 i

Table 2. First Five Non-Zero Eigenvalues for Isotropic Material

Eq. (17)	Eq. (20)
-0.0915	0.2094 ± 0.5832 i
-0.4555	1.5662 ± 0.8007 i
0.6293 ± 0.2313 i	2.9156 ± 0.9418 i
1.3013 ± 0.3158 i	4.2603 ± 1.0470 i
1.9718 ± 0.3739 i	5.6020 ± 1.1310 i

DISCUSSION

Results in Table 1 reveal a singularity in conjunction with both the [0°] and [0°/90°]_S composites. We note, however, that the singularity associated with the bidirectional laminate is weak.

For the isotropic case, considerably different results are obtained for the half notch case as opposed to the full notch. In the case of the full notch two singularities exist. The first singularity is very weak, while the second is on the order of a classic square root singularity. It should be noted that the second singularity is identical to the value reported by Williams [2]. As previously discussed, the full notch represents the case of general inplane loading and is not specific to the conditions of vanishing normal stress at the notch cross-section as obtained in the half notch. No singularity is obtained for the half notch, which would appear to verify some of the original conclusions made by Iosipescu concerning the v-notch shear test [1].

In conclusion, it is clear that a singularity may exist at the tip of a 90° notch in an orthotropic Iosipescu shear specimen. The existence and strength of a singularity will depend on basic unidirectional composite properties and laminate geometry. Future work should concentrate on extending the singularity analysis to other composite materials such as glass/epoxy and Kevlar. In addition a 120° notch should be investigated as this is also an often utilized geometry.

REFERENCES

1. N. Iosipescu, "New Accurate Procedure for Single Shear Testing of Metals, *Journal of Materials*, Vol. 2, No. 3, September, 1967, pp. 537-566.
2. M. L. Williams, "Stress Singularity Resulting From Various Boundary Conditions in Angular Corners of Plates in Extension," *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 19, Sept. 1952, pp. 526-528.

